

Problem-Solving in the Law Policy Implementation of Radio Frequency Spectrum in Indonesia

Marwan

Sekolah Tinggi Multi Media "MMTC" Yogyakarta, Indonesia
Email: marwansamsyul23@gmail.com

Abstract

Based on a proposition, the preferred interpretation method for problem-solving and the tools or media between the communicant and the communicator involve messages. These messages are used as feedback to understand the implied and expressed contents of the interaction. Although there is an interpretation of the communication law, its application to concrete events is unclear. Since the rule of text is clear and easy to understand, it is not used for multiple interpretations whose contained meaning needs to be interpreted correctly. The meaning of the communication policy can be interpreted, though it is not regulated in the law. However, it is prohibited if contrary to public order and morality, and this policy is permissible, providing it is required in terms of legal certainty, justice, and expediency. In practice, there is no priority in using interpretation methods. Hence, it can be used for separate occasions or synergized with several methods at once, and policy implementers are free and unbound to use them. Consequently, the important aspect for policy implementation is the ability to target legal certainty, justice, and benefit, alongside clarifying the provisions of these laws and regulations for the community in realizing the state's welfare. Public input is also needed to criticize communication policies and ensure it has and properly implements its value and benefits. With the issuance of ministerial and the Broadcasting Commission (KPI) regulations, there are special aspects that need to be considered. These are language, uniformity of terms or terminology, lengthy sentences, various unnecessary words, alongside the excessive use and problems resulting from reserves and exceptions, foreign language terms, official spellings, and the mention (*anhalen*) of statutory regulations. The issuance of a communication policy through a Ministerial Decree is progress in directing FM radio station activities to implement frequency channels on an ad-hoc basis. This implementation should occur through the authority of the central and regional KPI without ignoring the legal principles of the prevailing laws and regulations. Since the FM radio broadcasting policy implementation seems to be no different from being directed at the private radio-television broadcasting industry in Indonesia, democracy is needed for this context.

Keywords: Regulation, Policy, Frequency, Interpretation.

INTRODUCTION

According to Law No. 32 of 2002 concerning broadcasting, the radio frequency spectrum is a limited natural resource and national wealth that should be maintained and protected by the state. Also, it should be used for the people's greatest prosperity, in line with the objectives of the Indonesia proclamation on August 17, 1945. In the national broadcasting system referred to in paragraph (1), the state controls the radio frequency spectrum used for broadcasting related to community accomplishment.

Meanwhile, the radio frequency spectrum is an electromagnetic wave, which propagates in the air and space without artificial transmission means in the public domain, and is used for broadcasting. This spectrum, using FM transmitters or electromagnetic (micro) waves as transmission media, is very important for broadcasters from the public, private institutions, and the community, and in turning on related programs. Without radio waves as transmission, broadcasting institutions may not be able to function properly.

Regarding radio frequency, the government issued the Policy Implementation of the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of the Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band in Indonesia. The contents specify that every FM radio broadcasting operation (Frequency Modulation) should comply with the following technical provisions:

1. The radio frequency band used is 87.5 – 108 MHz;
2. Frequency channels used are multiples of 100 kHz;
3. The maximum frequency deviation is ± 75 kHz at 100% Modulation;
4. The transmitter frequency tolerance according to the Appendix Radio Regulation is 2000 Hz;
5. Spurious emission level minimum 60 dB below mean power level;

6. Bandwidth for maximum deviation of ± 75 kHz and 100% maximum modulation of 372 kHz;
7. The oscillator should have a center frequency stability of a maximum (+) 200 Hz and a maximum (-) 200 Hz from the center frequency.

Broadcasting institutions that use the frequency threshold of the transmitter area exceeding 800 Hz and 600Hz in and outside the city, respectively, escaped this state control. These include broadcasting equipment or Link by OB VAN Mobil as a modulation channel, the establishment of radio stations without a permit, and the theft of frequency channels using information technology tools. Meanwhile, government policies in the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 have been unable to complete the regulation of broadcasting frequency channels holistically. This is because the legal discourse of communication is not socialized to broadcasters, hence implementing the text meaning is ambiguous.

In this case, the state's function represented by the government and the community plays a very important role in supervising radio frequency channels. As stipulated in Law No. 32 of 2003 concerning broadcasting, Article 8 of the Indonesian Broadcasting Commission (KPI) has the authority to:

1. Set broadcast program standards;
2. Formulate regulations and establish a broadcasting code of conduct;
3. Supervise the implementation of regulations and guidelines for the broadcasting code of conduct and program standards;
4. Provide sanctions for violations of regulations and guidelines for the code of conduct and the program standards;
5. Coordinate and/or cooperate with the government, broadcasting institutions, and the public (Law No. 2 of 2002 concerning broadcasting).

Recently, private radio stations, central, provincial, city, district, and even village governments in Indonesia have had a strong will to seriously implement the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band. Therefore, this research proposes a question of communication law discourse regarding the extent to which the meaning created at the policy regulation text-maker (superstructure) level implements ministerial decisions. More specifically, it concerns how communication policies, through the creation of meaning (superstructure), are strongly influenced by economic, political, social, security, and other interests.

The value of the communication law discourse elements can be articulated to originate from the reality of the text, "Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band." Hence, this legal discourse of communication policy (text) based on justice, benefit, and legal certainty is accepted by the public.

METHOD

This research used a normative Semiotic truth method by specifically examining the sign system made as norms by humans (Burhan, 2001) to understand the meaning contained in the legislation text. Hermeneutics was a step to interpret the communication policy text messages according to laws and regulations, particularly the dogmatic relationship between communication law and theory (Romdhoni, 2019). Meanwhile, this research is limited only to the layer of legal discourse on micro-communication and communication theory.

The material and primary data were obtained through micro-communication research on the Policy Implementation of the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020. This research was analyzed by the following steps:

1. *The material aspects* were separated from the legal aspects of the communication policy and not events (facts).
2. *Determine* the data to be sought in answering the problem and how to interpret the policy contents by not expressing the general information, but that given about the variables in question.
3. *The frequency of legal events* analyzed by the communication legislation was legal facts, which are communication policy events (data) that are relatively inseparable from the research object.
4. Based on data that was conceptualized as an entity that only relates to factual information, the communication policies were analyzed, and the data obtained were evaluated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Concept for Evaluating the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band

Human behavior is caused by a complex line of thought, hence their actions can be interpreted and influenced by normative ideas. This thesis is closely related to the micro-communication law in finding the meaning of this behavior through the interpretation of the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020. Therefore, it can find the real argumentation and meaning construction and make the later appearance of the phrase, "*Het recht hink achter de feiten ann*," that the written law is always behind the events understandable.

The method of legal interpretation is performed in the case that the regulations exist, though their application to concrete events is unclear. Meanwhile, the interpretation of the regulatory text adheres to the sound, and not all words, terms, and sentences that indicate the rule of law and are expressed orally or written in legislation form are clear and easy to understand. Hence, the interpretation method involves interpreting the unclear legislation text to facilitate its application to certain concrete events. The interpretation teaching in the discovery of this law has long been known and called juridical hermeneutics.

Interpretation is performed by government policy judges and their communication law researchers dealing with cases or conflicts and related regulations. These interpretations by such individuals are explanations that should lead to the application or unapplication of communication law regulation to concrete events that are acceptable by the community. Von Savigny, in Sagio (2017), gave limitations on interpretation and explanation as a reconstruction of the thoughts inferred in the law. This is not a method that can be used arbitrarily but entails various activities that should be performed simultaneously to achieve the goal, which is the interpretation of the law.

Therefore, an important task for judges, government policies, and communications law researchers is to adapt laws to social realities. Law that is not implemented according to the word's meaning should be interpreted to ensure fair decisions are made in line with the legal purposes of communication, which are achieving legal certainty, justice, and expediency.

On that basis, interpreting communication law can be stated as a legal obligation of judges, government policies, and communication law researchers, although there are some restrictions. Logeman, in Hidayat (2013), stated that the parties mentioned above should submit to the will of lawmakers. In the event that the will cannot be read from the words of the legislation, it should be sought in the history of words, legal systems, and everyday words.

Each interpretation is limited by the legislator's will, and judges, government policies, and communication law researchers are not allowed to interpret the law arbitrarily. According to Candra, Einstein, & Helmi (2019), the method of interpretation is determined by a) the material of the relevant laws and regulations, b) the place where the case is filed, and c) according to the times. In practice, there is no priority in the use of interpretation methods, meaning they can be used independently, and several can be synergized simultaneously.

Therefore, although judges, government policies, and communication law researchers are free and unbound to use certain interpretation methods, they should be right on target, which is to clarify the legislative provisions and ensure proper application to events.

The use of various interpretations in the settlement of a case can result in different conclusions or disparities, as methods employed by these parties may differ, even when dealing with similar cases. However, the important matter is the acceptable or appropriate decision for those seeking legal certainty, justice, and the benefits of law and society in general. Although the attitude of judges, government policies, and communication law researchers in deciding cases is subjective, it does not involve the ego, as they should remain rational and logical to ensure their decisions are objective (Sudikno Martokusumo, 57-67:200).

Interpretation Differences in the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of the Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band.

There are many problems with the authority to interpret licenses in FM radio broadcasting frequencies, and this decision has been studied extensively and considered for review by the Minister of Communication and Information.

The aspects that changed in the revision of the Draft Regulation by the Minister of Communication and Informatics are as follows:

1. The addition of service areas that were unlisted in the previous Ministerial Decree (KM 15 of 2003) was from 457 to 1995.
2. This development is very reasonable because currently, there have been many regional expansions approved by the DPR, which have directly impacted technical regulations as stipulated in this draft.
3. The allotment for the addition of the service area is generally 3 channels.

4. The service area is mapped with a boundary line as a reference for the outermost point of the broadcast area. At the outermost point, the field strength is limited to a maximum of 66 dBuV/m.

This means that the frequency regulation aimed at providing community radio broadcasting services is no longer limited to 3 channels. However, this determination is with the provision that technical analysis is performed by the Director-General of Post and Telecommunication. The channel is also stipulated to fulfill the technical provisions for radio service broadcasting. Finally, a condition that the use of the radio frequency channel does not cause harmful interference against other similar licensed channels and/or the operation of broadcasting services using FM radio frequencies according to the channel mapping in each service area in this Ministerial Regulation.

Therefore, the state needs interpretation, argumentation, and construction of the difference to discover the law of communication and prevent obscurity. Examples of differences are the Grammatical Interpretation of Licensing Cases Controlling, alongside the sealing of Radio Suara Metro and other radios operating based on a permit from the Department of Transportation, which tend to be "resisted" by their owners. The reason is they have permits that are also legally valid under the provisions of section 17 (a) of Article 2 (3) of Government Regulation (PP) No. 25/2000 concerning Government Authorities and Provincial Government Authorities as Autonomous Regions.

In essence, the provisions of the Government Regulation state that the central government is authorized to regulate the national telecommunication system, as well as the granting of radio orbits and frequencies, except for local radio and TV. This exclusion is the trigger for provincial governments in various regions to issue licenses for frequency allocation and radio broadcasting operations.

The provisions of Law No. 36/1999 on Telecommunications and its implementing regulations state that the Director-General of Post and Telecommunication is authorized to issue frequency allocation permits. Meanwhile, Law No. 32/2002 on Broadcasting expressly affirmed that the radio broadcasting operation permit is granted by the state through the Indonesian Broadcasting Commission (KPI) Article 33.

Consequently, the question is, which of these institutions has the most right to issue frequency allocation and radio broadcast operation permits? The legal principle explains *Lex posteriori derogate legi priori*, meaning 'The new law weakens the old law, and the new law applies if it contradicts the old law, which regulates the same material.'

Interpretation in this context is needed to resolve broadcasting legal issues and decide the authority to interpret communication policy decisions between institutions. This interpretation concerns the most fully entitled institution to be first decided by the Supreme Court (MA) as authorized to conduct a judicial review of legal provisions with a level under the Act.

Subsequently, the question regarding the party authorized to submit legal decisions to the Supreme Court arises. Although everyone has the right to apply to the Supreme Court, the judge decides by objective interpretation. Both parties interpret the existing laws and regulations differently and should have remedies to obtain legal certainty. The Director-General of Post and Telecommunication is an authorized institution to regulate and monitor the use of frequencies. This institution submitted a legal decision containing an application for a permit issued by the Department of Transportation and formulated as a regional regulation regarding Government Regulation No. 25/2000, which was declared null and void. The legal principle of *Lex specialis derogate legi generali*, meaning 'Special laws weaken or overpower general laws in the event of a conflict,' took precedence because the Government Regulation violates the applicable laws and regulations. Furthermore, lower legal provisions, such as regional regulations and Government Regulation No 25/2000, should not conflict with higher legal provisions, like Law No 36/1999 and Law No 32/2002.

The interpretation meaning of communication policy regulations with the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of the Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band

These laws and regulations are legal protection for the formulation of communication policy regulations under them, as well as other laws and regulations that have a broadcasting law dimension, especially FM Radio frequencies. The legal principle of *Lex specialis derogate legi generali* (special law weakens or overpowers the general law in the event of a conflict), which is used to implement communication policies, was raised in Law No. 32 of 2002 concerning Broadcasting.

Chapter I Article 1 paragraph 8 states, 'The radio frequency spectrum, which is an electromagnetic wave used for broadcasting and propagating in the air and space without artificial means of conduction, is a public domain and has limited natural resources.' This was implemented through Government Regulation No. 53 of 2000 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum and Satellite Orbit and Government policy of Decree of the Minister of Transportation No. 15 of 2003 concerning Regulation of FM Radio Frequency Channel.

In retrospect, the broadcasting laws and regulations in Law no. 32 of 2003 concerning broadcasting are inseparable from the preamble stated in letter b. This preamble states that the radio frequency spectrum is a limited natural resource and

a national asset that should be safeguarded and protected by the state. Also, it should be used for the greatest prosperity of the people according to the Proclamation 17 August 1945 ideals.

This context shows that a link exists between radio broadcasting activities and the spectrum through radiation and/or transmission on land, at sea, or in space using a radio frequency spectrum via air, cable, and/or other media to be received simultaneously by the public with broadcast receivers.

Furthermore, the broadcasting policy content in this country is very legalistic and emphasizes the principle regarding freedom of expression without rules in conveying information.

Consequently, the community considers the information conveyed to the public as confusing and ambiguous and hopes the government will immediately improve and replace the information system as shown on the screen, printed media with responsible, true, and factual information. This makes regulating the legal discourse of communication necessary (Kincaid, 1979):

1. Broadcast.
2. Broadcasting.
3. Television broadcasting.
4. Broadcast advertising, Broadcast commercial ads
5. Broadcast public service advertisements.
6. Radio frequency spectrum.
7. Broadcasting agency.
8. National broadcasting system.
9. A fair, equitable, and balanced national information order.
10. Government.
11. Indonesian Broadcasting Commission.
12. Broadcasting operation license.

To answer the issue of legal discourse on the use of frequency communication, the ontological basis of the communication will be analyzed as follows:

1. Law No. 32 of 2002 concerning broadcasting.
2. Government Regulation Number 53 of 2000 concerning Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum and Satellite Orbit.
3. Decree of the Transportation Minister No. 15 of 2003 concerning Regulation of FM Radio Frequency Channels.
4. Decree of the Transportation Minister Number: km. 27 of 2004.
5. Regarding the Stipulation and Procedures for Diverting Radio Frequency Channels for Operators of FM Broadcasting Radio (Frequency Modulation) by the Minister of Transportation.

Freedom to express opinions, convey, and obtain information comes from the people's sovereignty and is a human right in the life of a democratic society, nation, and state. Therefore, independence or freedom in broadcasting should be guaranteed by the state.

The meaning of the Decree of the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band on Event Programs.

Many FM Radio programs are used for the benefit of the government and society. During the new cycle, news broadcasting programs were used to make statements, as performed by the government. However, there is a bias of information by all groups, and the government is not accepted as the only wrong party, as the mass media is also involved in spreading information. Indeed, the establishment of the public sphere has always relied on the fact that the mass media has a great side.

Radio-television and print media show that the audience is not just consumers or information products but active actors and agents that help shape social reality. Also, the experience of electronic and print mass media shows that the establishment of the public sphere seems to be one of the most important agendas in every news report, as a place for various dialogues, opinions, and sympathy.

Public Sphere: Habermas observed that the bourgeois public sphere has provided space for people in a position between the market and the state, alongside between the economy and government since the beginning. The people in question are professionals, such as academics, lawyers, doctors, and civil servants, and have the privilege to enjoy the sphere. A pillar related to an effective public is the mass media, especially in the process of news dissemination and critical analysis of the government's work.

Currently, mass media, including electronic and print, are often criticized as a structure that perpetuates the various interests of the two mutually attractive powers in society, which are the State and the market or capital. The media is used as a hegemonic tool that can create safe and controlled conditions for the State's interests. Meanwhile, according

to the experience of the New Order era, it should first be subdued through the threat of banning to achieve this function. Based on the cultural point of view today, the development of mass media is characterized by various tendencies, such as:

1. *Convergence* occurs when a variety of different media newspapers, radio, television, telephone, and the internet, are merged technologically and economically.
2. *Concentration* takes place when media companies are combined in one platform and controlled by one or more common owners.
3. *Globalization* occurs when the media is owned by multinational companies that can cross various boundaries of space and time.
4. *Commercialization* describes when the insertion of advertising into entertainment programs and news began, making the distance among them often unclear. Commercial influence occurs when advertisers and media owners influence various editorial policies.
5. *Trivialization* is when sex and violence become mainstream, celebrities' private lives are exposed, and the media rejects serious and controversial debates.

Public Sphere and Media Credibility: Many experts try to identify the qualities that should be in a news story. Does every news have to represent actual, sharp, and reliable elements? Although at first glance, that quality is an idea from the newsroom's owner or manager, it is actually a collection of effects or impacts that can be taken and is based on the public's determination. Normatively, this serves as a code of ethics that should be obeyed by every media newsroom. Meanwhile, the code of ethics contained in the electronic media seems slightly more derived from the printed platform, and news should be precise or accurate, complete, fair, and balanced, will not be expected to mix facts and opinions.

In short, news must be objective and, as a practical requirement for writing, concise, clear, and warm. Even this quality is legalized in the code of ethics used by print media journalists in Article 5 of the Indonesian journalistic code of ethics. This code states that Indonesian journalists present news in a balanced and fair manner, prioritize accuracy, and not mix facts and opinions.

Gaziano and McGrath in Khussari (2018) identified 12 dimensions of credibility contained in print and electronic media. These are completeness, accuracy, respect for private matters, supervising the interests of individuals, concern for the community, separation of facts and opinions, truth, concern for a public interest, factual, and level of reporter training. However, Gaziano and McGrath were criticized by Rogers & Kincaid (1981) that the twelve dimensions were not juxtaposed on theoretical understanding, hence validity does not represent the reality.

The commodification process of information and news has subjugated the public as obedient products, objects, commodities, and consumers. This is due to the increasingly familiar political and economic interests built by the government and held by several media corporations, respectively.

Also, this occurs in various processes in media cultures, such as convergence, centralization, globalization, commercialization, and the influence of trivialization. Awareness that the role of the information manager is a strategic position in the government is necessary, and the functions include restoring public trust. This is done using spinning techniques, manipulating, and twisting various information to overcome crises, which can secretly shift the importance of establishing the public sphere. Furthermore, public opinion and pluralism of ideas will never work.

Therefore, the content of the broadcasting law policy, especially frequency in this country, can be understood as very legalistic and emphasizing the legal certainty principles, community benefits, and justice in the use of radio and television broadcasting. However, based on the results of a deductive and inductive study, the regulation does not consider the community interests nor the value of public education but is more concerned with business and politics. This can be seen from various radio-television broadcasts when viewed from their function in using the frequency to ensure all parts of the country can receive their programs.

The implementation process of the meaning related to the Radio Frequency Spectrum and Satellite Orbit and the issuance of the Ministerial Decree of the Communication and Information Technology Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of the Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band.

The study of the implementation process on special broadcasting policies for FM Radio is inseparable from the issue that frequency is a limited natural resource that should be regulated for the common interest of the State and society. In this effort, a policy on Government Regulation Number 53 of 2000 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum and Satellite Orbit was issued. The Policy Implementation related to the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band in Indonesia was also issued.

Furthermore, the government took steps as an implementation process, including the determination of the KPI organization. The FM radio policy, as authorized by the government regarding communication, is expected to coordinate

various radio and television communication sectors, including programs and frequencies. Based on the results, the meaning of the two policies is closely related to the implementation of broadcasting policies in Indonesia. Therefore, in studying the implementation process, two policies need to be specifically examined as follows:

Policy Analysis on FM Radio Frequency Licensing.

The government issued a policy for the radio and television broadcasting community with various regulations to prevent disturbance by other frequencies. Hence, broadcasters that do not comply with the frequency regulations regarding the use of electromagnetic waves, which is a very serious limited natural resource for radio and television broadcast programs, may cause negative impacts. There is a new concept in the broadcasting policy based on Law no. 10 of 2004 concerning the formation of legislation, represented by the Indonesian Broadcasting Commission (KPI). This policy, which regulates KPI's authority, is similar to other legal institutions that can revoke licenses from broadcasting institutions in violation of the law.

Radio broadcasting stations appear to have been integrated into the licensing process. Hence, the issuance of Law No. 32 of 2003 concerning broadcasting related to radio licenses and the cancellation of the Constitutional Court's decision regarding the authority of KPI and the government was unwise. Subsequently, the Broadcasting law product of Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band was issued. This law requires all FM radio broadcasters to follow the policy outlined by the Ministry of Transportation. It was implemented to make Law No. 32 of 2003 concerning broadcasting and Government Regulation No. 53 of 2000 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum and Satellite Orbit effective in broadcasting activities, especially FM frequency.

Consequently, the ministerial regulation of information communication should be issued to regulate broadcasting, and this can be implemented by the Indonesian Broadcasting Commission (KPI). Also, Radio FM, which has been operating in broadcast programs, is directed to perform evaluation studies and broadcast documents. These steps are guided by the decree of the transportation and communication ministers, alongside the KPIs, to evaluate the determination of future work programs.

A standard operating procedure or benchmark for frequency use is required by broadcasting policies, especially FM radio, to provide guidelines for other stations and prevent frequency channel theft due to limited natural resources. The government and KPI representing the community have set frequency standards to deal with theft and use of frequencies above the threshold. However, the broadcasting sector is yet to know whether the frequency usage is above or below, as not all thresholds can be measured by the Decree of the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020. Furthermore, the legal regulation of frequency for broadcasting in Indonesia regarding theft and the use above the threshold, as regulated in Law No. 32 of 2003 concerning broadcasting, has not been implemented properly (law Enforcement).

Meanwhile, the government considers important the issuance of a Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number: 17/P/M.Kominfo/6/2006 concerning Procedures to Adjust Broadcasting Operation Permits for Private Broadcasting Institutions. This includes those that already have Radio Station Permits or Subscription Broadcasting Institutions that have a Pay Television Service Operation Permit from the Director-General of Post and Telecommunication and/or National Broadcasting Permits for Television from the Ministry of Information.

FM Radio Policy Output: Analysis of Evaluative Studies on the Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band.

The initial implementation of the frequency policy at radio stations was not fully responded to by government and private stations. Lately, extensive interference from FM radio on frequency waves results in a strong will from private radio stations, central, provincial, city, and district governments to implement the policy seriously.

Consequently, the meanings of implementing this decree concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band from the central to village governments throughout Indonesia are:

1. broadcasting should guarantee and protect oral and written freedom of expression, including freedom of creation based on the principles of justice, democracy, and the rule of law;
2. broadcasting should reflect justice and democracy by balancing the rights and obligations of the community or government, including the human rights of each individual or person by respecting and not interfering with others;
3. considering all aspects of national and state life and broadcasting as important and strategic national and international economic institutions;
4. anticipating the development of communication and information technology, particularly in the broadcasting field, such as digital technology, compression, computerization, cable television, satellite, internet, and other special forms;

5. further empowering the community to exercise social control and participate in advancing national broadcasting. Therefore, the Indonesian Broadcasting Commission was formed to accommodate the community aspirations and represent the public interest in broadcasting;
6. broadcasting has a close relationship with radio frequency spectrum and geostationary satellite orbit, which are limited natural resources whose utilization needs to be managed effectively and efficiently;
7. broadcasting development is directed at the creation of quality and dignified broadcasts, capable of absorbing and reflecting the diverse aspirations of the community to increase the deterrence of the bad influence of foreign cultural values.

CONCLUSION

This is a reflection of the implied and explicit meaning of the policy in Communication and Information Technology Ministry Regulation Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Use of Radio Frequency Spectrum in the 2.3 GHz Band throughout Indonesia that:

1. Based on a proposition, the preferred interpretation method in problem-solving and the tools or media between the communicant and the communicator are messages as feedback to understand the implied and expressed contents.
2. Although there is an interpretation of the communication law, its application to concrete events is unclear. Since the meaning contained needs to be interpreted correctly, the rule text is not used for multiple interpretations, as it is clear and easy to understand.
3. The meaning of the communication policy can be interpreted, though it is unregulated in the law, but is prohibited if contrary to public order and morality. On the other hand, it is permissible, providing it is required in terms of legal certainty, justice, and expediency.
4. In the communication policy practice, there is no priority in the use of interpretation methods. Therefore, it can be used separately and synergized with several methods at once, where policy implementers are free or unbound to use certain interpretations methods. However, the important aspect for policy implementation is to target legal certainty, justice, and benefit and clarify the provisions of these laws and regulations for the community at large in realizing the welfare state.
5. Public input is needed to criticize Communication policies and ensure it has value and benefits and can be implemented appropriately.
6. With the issuance of ministerial and the Broadcasting Commission (KPI) regulations, special aspects need to be considered. These include language, uniformity of terms or terminology, lengthy sentences, various unnecessary words, excessive use and problems arising from reserves and exceptions, foreign language terms, official spellings, and the mention (*anhalen*) of statutory regulations.
7. The issuance of a communication policy formulated as a Ministerial Decree is progress in directing the FM radio station activities to implement frequency channels on an ad-hoc basis. Although this is performed through the authority of the central and regional KPI, the legal principles of the prevailing laws and regulations are not ignored.
8. The implementation of FM radio broadcasting policy appears similar to being directed at the private radio-television broadcasting industry in Indonesia, hence democracy is needed for this context.

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